

Layered Ego Networks in Email Communication: From Enron to the Jmail Archive

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Abstract. Email archives offer a rare view of social relationships through repeated communication, but it remains unclear how well classical ego-network layering applies to digital interaction data. This paper compares two public email archives with sharply contrasting structures: Enron, a workplace corpus involving around 150 users, and Jmail, a single-ego archive centered on an exceptionally active focal actor whose communication volume is more than twenty times higher than the average Enron user. We ask, in each case, whether Dunbar-like layered organization is recoverable from email communication frequency and how it should be interpreted. For Jmail, we show that extreme communication intensity causes standard layering methods (whether clustering-based or threshold-based) to break down. Jmail is not a broad communication environment with many occasional contacts, but a selective pool of high-interest alters operating on a much higher frequency scale than ordinary email. Once the Dunbar frequency ladder is anchored to the empirical support-clique boundary, a clearer layered structure emerges. Reciprocity analysis confirms that the recovered layers reflect genuine bidirectional relationships rather than artifacts of the focal actor’s outgoing activity. Enron serves as a workplace benchmark that grounds the comparison: its ego networks partially reproduce Dunbar-like organization, with stable inner circles and an outer layer close to the Dunbar ~ 50 reference, confirming that layered structure is recoverable from ordinary organizational email. Overall, the findings show that Dunbar-like organization can be meaningfully studied in email archives, but that selective high-frequency archives require frequency normalization before the layered structure becomes interpretable.

Keywords: Email Communication · Ego networks · Dunbar’s model · Temporal dynamics · Enron · Jmail

1 Introduction

Email is one of the oldest and most persistent forms of digital communication, yet it remains among the least studied from a social network perspective. Unlike platforms designed for public sharing, email encodes social relationships through

repeated private interaction: ties are not declared but enacted, message by message, over months and years. This makes email logs a uniquely faithful record of real communicative investment. Yet the same properties that make email valuable also make it difficult to study. Privacy constraints, limited accessibility, and the sensitivity of personal correspondence keep public datasets scarce, with only a handful of widely used resources available for research [10, 15, 12].

This scarcity has a concrete cost for ego-network research [7]. Ego networks provide a user-centered view of social structure, placing a focal individual (the ego) at the center and representing their contacts (the alters) as a surrounding personal network. Rather than studying global network topology, ego-network analysis asks how communication is distributed across an individual’s contacts and how stronger and weaker ties organize within that personal sphere. A central finding of this literature is that personal networks are not flat collections of contacts but are organized into discrete layers of increasing size and decreasing interaction intensity [6, 7]. In Dunbar’s model, these layers follow a canonical structure: a support clique of around 5 alters contacted at least weekly, a sympathy group of around 15 contacted at least monthly, an affinity group of around 50 contacted at least every six months, and an active network of around 150 contacted at least yearly. Successive layers scale by a ratio of approximately 3, and interaction frequency drops correspondingly as one moves outward. More recently, an innermost layer of just 1–2 alters has been identified, representing the ego’s closest and most frequently contacted ties [7]. Crucially, this structure is thought to reflect cognitive and time constraints on relationship maintenance rather than platform-specific affordances, which is why it has been proposed as a universal feature of human social networks. Prior work has confirmed that these patterns are not confined to offline relationships but re-emerge in digital communication traces, including mobile-phone calls and online social platforms [1, 2, 13], and have recently been observed in decentralized social media as well [4]. Yet email remains comparatively underexplored as a setting for testing Dunbar-like ego-network organization. It is therefore still unclear whether ego networks extracted from email communication reproduce layered organization in both circle size and contact frequency.

This paper addresses that gap directly. We analyse two public email archives with sharply contrasting structures and ask, in each case, whether layered ego-network organization is recoverable and how it should be interpreted. The first archive is Enron, a large organizational corpus involving around 150 users whose complete mailboxes were made public during a federal investigation. Despite being one of the most studied datasets in email network research, its ego-network structure has never been examined through the lens of Dunbar-style layering. We use it as a workplace benchmark: a setting in which communication is recurrent and role-structured, and in which Dunbar-like layering, if present, should be most clearly visible. Our analysis shows that it is: Enron users can be organized into layered personal networks with progressively larger and less frequently contacted circles, providing the first explicit evaluation of Dunbar-like ego-network structure in workplace email.

We then use this baseline to study Jmail, a rare and structurally unusual archive. Jmail is centered on a single, highly active focal actor whose communication record spans approximately ten years and involves thousands of distinct contacts, at a volume more than twenty times higher than the average Enron user. Public email datasets are rare; large archives centered on a single socially salient individual and available for research are rarer still. This makes Jmail a valuable but non-standard test case: it does not represent ordinary email communication, but a selective, partially redacted record of an exceptionally intense ego-centered communication space. Applying standard ego-network methods to such an archive is non-trivial, and understanding where and why they break down (and how they can be recovered) is of both methodological and empirical interest.

Against this background, this work makes three contributions. First, it characterizes Jmail as a rare and structurally unusual ego-centered archive in which extreme communication intensity causes the standard methods for obtaining Dunbar’s circles (whether clustering-based or threshold-based) to break down, and shows that rescaling contact-frequency thresholds to the archive’s communication intensity recovers a meaningful layered structure, confirmed as genuinely bidirectional through reciprocity analysis. Second, it evaluates Dunbar-like ego-network layers in email communication, using Enron as a workplace benchmark that grounds the comparison and makes the unusual properties of Jmail interpretable. Third, it shows that Dunbar’s model is robust across these contrasting regimes: layered organization emerges in ordinary workplace email and can be recovered in high-volume ego-centered archives alike, provided that frequency thresholds are adapted to the communication scale of the dataset.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews ego-network studies in offline, online, and email-based social environments. Section 3 describes the email archives and the construction of layered ego networks. Section 4 presents the empirical analysis, including the Enron ego-network analysis, the emergence of Dunbar-like structures in email, the contrasting organization of Jmail, and the comparison between data-driven, direct Dunbar-based, and rescaled Dunbar-style groupings. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Related works

This work connects ego-network research, where interaction frequency distinguishes stronger and weaker ties around an ego, with email-based social network analysis, where communication logs reveal temporal rhythms, roles, communities, and organizational structure.

Ego networks in offline and online environments. Ego-network research has shown that personal social networks are not homogeneous collections of contacts, but tend to be organized into layers of increasing size and decreasing interaction intensity. This regularity is usually associated with Dunbar’s model, where alters are arranged around the ego in concentric circles, from a small support core to a broader active network [6, 7]. Table 1 summarizes the offline reference sizes and contact-frequency thresholds provided by Dunbar, which we will use later in the

Table 1: Reference properties of offline ego-network layers.

Layer number	Layer name	Description	Alters	Scaling ratio (alters)	Contact frequency
1	Support clique	close family	5		once every week
2	Sympathy group	close friends	15	~ 3	once a month
3	Affinity group	friends/extended family/ colleagues	50		once every 6 months
4	Active network	meaningful relationships	150		once a year

paper. Empirical studies in online social networks have shown that digital platforms can reproduce comparable ego-network constraints, despite differences in interaction cost and medium [1, 2]. Interestingly, these online studies have also revealed an innermost layer of just 1–2 alters, representing the ego’s closest and most frequently contacted ties, which is not part of the canonical offline model but emerges consistently in digital interaction data [7]. Similar layered patterns have also been observed in mobile-phone communication, where call frequency is used to cluster alters into ego-network layers comparable to Dunbar’s predicted circle sizes [13]. More recent ego-centered analyses of decentralized social platforms have extended this perspective to newer forms of online interaction [4]. These works provide the structural reference for the present study. They show that layered ego networks can be recovered from behavioral traces, and that interaction frequency is a meaningful proxy for tie strength. However, most evidence comes from offline relationships, online social platforms, or mobile-phone communication. Email remains comparatively less explored from this perspective, and prior work has not systematically asked whether email-derived ego networks recover Dunbar-like layers in terms of both circle size and contact frequency.

Emails and social network analysis. Email has long been used to study social structure, organizational communication, and temporal interaction dynamics. Early work showed that email logs can reveal communities of practice within organizations, using message exchange as a proxy for information flow and social proximity [16]. Other studies emphasized temporal organization: Barabási showed that human actions, including email activity, are bursty and heavy-tailed rather than Poisson-like [3], while Eckmann, Moses, and Sergi showed that email traffic contains coherent dialogue structures based on repeated and synchronized exchanges [8]. Large-scale messaging studies also found strong daily and weekly rhythms, burstiness, and uneven activity across users and ties [9]. Together, these results indicate that email and messaging networks are heterogeneous both in time and across relationships. A second line of work has focused on the structure and evolution of email networks. Kossinets and Watts analysed a university email network of 43,553 individuals over one academic year, showing that tie formation is shaped by organizational affiliation, similarity, and triadic closure [11]. In the Enron corpus, Diesner and Carley extracted communication networks from the email archive and showed that the network became denser, more centralized, and more connected during the organizational crisis [5]. McCallum et al. combined email structure and content to discover topics and roles in Enron and academic email, showing that communication patterns are shaped by sender–recipient re-

lations and organizational roles [14]. These studies establish Enron as one of the main benchmarks for email-based social network analysis, but they mainly focus on global network structure, community organization, roles, crisis dynamics, or topic-aware interaction patterns.

The present work differs from this literature by using Enron as a benchmark for ego-network layer extraction in workplace email and Jmail as an extreme-frequency ego-centered archive. To the best of our knowledge, prior email-network studies have documented skewed communication, bursty timing, strong and weak tie regimes, and dense organizational cores, but have not translated these patterns into a longitudinal Dunbar-style ego-network analysis. Our contribution is therefore a comparison between a conventional workplace corpus and a selective high-contact archive, aimed at testing when Dunbar-like structure is visible, distorted, or recoverable through frequency scaling.

3 Methodology

3.1 Email Archives

We ground our analysis in two public email archives that differ sharply in scope and structure, allowing us to test layered ego-network methods in a conventional organizational setting before applying them to a more unusual ego-centered archive.

Enron email corpus. One of the most widely used public datasets for the study of email communication. The version used in this work is the Carnegie Mellon University CALO Project release.³ The corpus contains approximately half a million messages from about 150 users, mostly members of Enron senior management. The data were originally made public by the Federal Energy Regulatory Commission during its investigation of Enron. In the present study, Enron serves as a large-scale organizational benchmark, representative of a conventional workplace communication setting. Table 2 reports statistics at two stages of the processing pipeline. *Nodes* and *Links* describe the global communication graph. *Unique emails* counts original messages prior to recipient expansion, whereas *Interactions* counts exploded sender–recipient pairs; consequently, a single email sent to multiple recipients contributes multiple interactions. The ego-level columns (*Egos*, *Alters*, and *Alter-Egos*) are defined only for the selected scope, which is restricted to the 158 users with complete mailboxes. This restriction is necessary because only these users support full ego-network reconstruction. Within this subset, the dataset contains 91,990 unique emails, 115,384 interactions, 11,811 alters, and 151 egos that also appear as alters in other ego networks.

Jmail. The second dataset is based on a publicly released archival email collection.⁴ The collection documents the email activity of a high-profile public figure whose correspondence was released as part of a legal investigation. In its original distribution, the material consists primarily of redacted PDF files, which makes

³ <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~enron/>

⁴ We study Jmail as a public archival dataset and focus only on aggregate communication structure. The analysis does not infer private attributes of individuals or evaluate the content of messages.

Table 2: Summary statistics of the Enron and Jmail datasets. Note that both graphs are directed. Ego-Alters are egos who also appear as alters in other ego networks.

	Nodes	Links	Uniq. emails	Interactions	Egos	Alters	Ego-Alters
Enron (raw)	35,848	104,449	495,554	730,852	—	—	—
Enron (selected)	11,818	22,249	91,990	115,384	158	11,811	151
Jmail (raw)	82,968	185,539	1,148,096	1,293,703	—	—	—
Jmail (selected)	4,299	4,299	287,630	308,515	1	4,299	—

Table 3: Activity intensity for Enron and Jmail main actors.

Dataset	Scope	Egos	Period of activity [days]	Interactions/day	Messages/day
Enron	Main actors	158	536.66 ± 251.63	1.20 ± 1.50	0.93 ± 1.14
Jmail	Main actor	1	13192	23.37	21.79

direct computational analysis non-trivial. We ultimately relied on the structured email representation provided through Jmail⁵, which has become a de facto reference format for accessing this collection and also functions as an API-like access layer allowing direct retrieval of the public data. Unlike Enron, Jmail is not a broad organizational corpus: it is centered on one main actor whose core activity spans approximately ten years, offering a selective and partially redacted view of a highly active ego-centered communication space.

Table 2 reports the statistics about the Jmail dataset. The ego-level columns are defined only for the selected scope, which is restricted to the single main actor around whom the archive is organized. Within this scope, the dataset contains 287,630 unique emails, 308,515 interactions, and 4,299 alters. Additional details on preprocessing, identity consolidation, and filtering are reported in Appendix A. Table 3 provides additional information about Enron and Jmail at the ego level. Although Jmail contains only one focal ego, this ego is observed over a much longer lifespan and produces substantially higher activity than the average Enron main actor. In particular, the Jmail main actor produces 21.79 messages per day, compared with 0.93 messages per day for Enron main actors on average, i.e., more than twenty times higher activity. This confirms that Jmail is not simply a smaller ego-centered version of Enron, but an unusually intense single-ego archive.

3.2 Ego network Extraction

We provide here a concise description of the ego-network extraction procedure, as it follows standard methods widely adopted in the related literature [7]. For both archives, we represent email communication as a directed ego–alter network. Each email is converted into sender–recipient interactions: the sender is treated as the ego and each recipient as an alter. When a message has multiple recipients, it contributes one directed interaction for each sender–recipient pair.

⁵ <https://jmail.world>. The Jmail file used in the present work is `jmail_data/v1/emails.parquet`

Before constructing the ego networks, we remove invalid records, missing identities, self-loops, duplicated interactions, and timestamps outside the selected observation windows.

Eligible egos are defined differently in the two datasets. In Enron, we consider only users represented by an individual mailbox folder, so that each ego has a comparable mailbox-level communication environment. In Jmail, the primary ego is the main actor around whom the archive is organized (by leveraging an apposite column indicating his identity). The basic unit of analysis is the ego–alter dyad within a yearly window. For each ego and each alter, we count the number of observed directed interactions in that year. The procedure is applied to the core activity periods of the two datasets. For Enron, ego networks are extracted year by year for 2000 and 2001, which correspond to the main activity period retained in our analysis. For Jmail, yearly ego-network snapshots are extracted from 2009 to 2018, capturing the core longitudinal activity of the focal actor and of the alters for whom ego-network reconstruction is possible.

Layer extraction is performed only on active alters. Following Dunbar’s model, an alter is considered active, i.e., occupying cognitive space in the ego’s social network, only if the relationship meets a minimum level of sustained engagement: the ego–alter relation must span at least six months, involve at least two directed interactions, and include at least one interaction in the calendar year considered. This minimum threshold of roughly one contact per year reflects Dunbar’s definition of a socially meaningful tie; alters that fall below it are retained for descriptive purposes but are not assigned to any social circle. The goal of layer extraction is to identify the ego’s social circles, i.e., the concentric groups of alters that correspond to Dunbar’s layers. Following the standard approach in the literature [13], we recover these circles by clustering active alters according to their annual interaction frequency with the ego: alters contacted at similar rates are grouped together, and the resulting clusters are interpreted as social circles. Specifically, we use MeanShift clustering (a common choice in the related literature [2]), which has the practical advantage of not requiring the number of circles to be fixed in advance, allowing the empirical layering to emerge directly from the observed frequency distribution. Clustering is performed independently for each ego and year, and the resulting circles are ordered by decreasing mean annual frequency: circle 1 contains the highest-frequency alters, with subsequent circles containing progressively less frequently contacted alters. These data-driven circles provide the baseline empirical layering used in the comparison with Dunbar-based and rescaled Dunbar-style interpretations.

4 Results

We report the results in two stages. We first use Enron as a conventional workplace-email benchmark to test whether layered ego-network organization can be recovered from ordinary organizational communication (Sec. 4.1). We then (Sec. 4.2) turn to Jmail, a substantially more extreme ego-centered archive, and show that standard Dunbar-style extraction methods break down under very high communication intensity. Finally, we show that rescaling the Dunbar frequency ladder

(a) Enron — Average daily activity

(b) Hourly activity

(c) Weekday activity

Fig. 1: Enron (2000-2001) — Temporal activity patterns of mailbox egos restores an interpretable layered structure that remains reciprocally meaningful from both ego and alter perspectives.

4.1 Enron as a Workplace Email Benchmark

Temporal activity patterns. Figure 1 shows that Enron activity is concentrated in 2000 and 2001 and follows the expected rhythms of workplace communication: activity increases during working hours, declines in the evening, and drops substantially during weekends. These patterns confirm that Enron provides a conventional organizational communication environment against which the more unusual structure of Jmail can later be interpreted.

Ego-network structure. We then narrow the analysis to the most active years, where ego networks are more likely to be sufficiently populated and structurally informative. Year 2001 counts 156 active egos, while the second most populated year is 2000 with 127. We thus focus on 2001 for our comparisons with Jmail. Among the active Enron ego networks in 2001, the most common configurations contain between four and seven circles: 24 egos exhibit four circles, 30 exhibit five circles, 22 exhibit six circles, and 25 exhibit seven circles, with five-circle structures being the most frequent case. We therefore focus on the five-circle egos in 2001. When looking at the size and interaction frequency for their circles, Figure 2 shows that Enron partially reproduces the layered organization predicted by Dunbar’s model. Cumulative circle sizes close to ~ 5 , ~ 15 , and ~ 50 alters emerge consistently across years, while the broader ~ 150 layer is not

Fig. 2: Enron — Five-circle ego-network structure in the most active years

recovered. Instead, an additional innermost layer of approximately ~ 3 alters appears, consistent with prior observations of digitally mediated ego networks. In frequency terms, the strongest correspondence with the Dunbar reference appears in the outermost observed layer. Although this layer has the size of the Dunbar ~ 50 circle rather than the ~ 150 circle, its average contact frequency is close to the corresponding semiannual threshold: approximately 3 messages per year, compared with 2 in the Dunbar model. The inner circles recover Dunbar-like sizes but at lower-than-expected frequencies, suggesting that organizational email captures the structural skeleton of personal networks but compresses the frequency range relative to offline interaction.

Key Finding 1: Workplace email recovers partial Dunbar-like structure

Enron produces stable ego-network layers that broadly resemble Dunbar-style organization. Small inner circles and an outer ~ 50 layer emerge consistently, but the broader ~ 150 layer is absent, suggesting that workplace email primarily captures recurrent organizational ties rather than complete personal social networks.

4.2 Breakdown and Recovery of Layered Structure in Jmail

We now apply the same analysis to Jmail, the focal archive for evaluating Dunbar-like ego-network organization in a high-frequency ego-centered setting. The Enron benchmark established that Dunbar-like layering is recoverable from workplace email; the question here is whether it remains recoverable when communication is unusually intense. We proceed in four steps: temporal activity, empirical ego-network layers, Dunbar-reference assignment and scaling, and reciprocity.

Temporal activity patterns. Figure 3 reports daily, hourly, and weekday activity for the Jmail main ego. The core period spans 2009–2018, with an average of approximately 64 messages per active day—roughly one hundred times the Enron average. Unlike Enron, hourly activity is lowest during standard working hours and rises sharply after 16:00, peaking around 19:00–20:00, with substantial activity also at night and in the early morning. The weekday profile is broadly similar to Enron, with higher activity early in the week and a gradual decline toward the weekend, though activity remains high across all days. Together, these

Fig. 3: Jmail (2009-2018) — Temporal activity patterns of the main ego.

patterns confirm that Jmail is not a workplace archive: its temporal rhythm reflects personal rather than organizational communication.

Empirical ego-network layers. With this context in mind, we ask whether the higher communication intensity observed in Jmail produces stable ego-network layers. Figure 4(a) summarizes the empirical MeanShift circles extracted from annual ego–alter interaction frequencies. Two features stand out. First, as in Enron, an additional inner layer of approximately ~ 3 alters emerges. Second, unlike Enron, Jmail reaches the broader ~ 150 -alter scale, consistent with a more complete personal network. However, the empirical structure is highly unbalanced: inner circles are very small while the outermost circle concentrates the majority of active alters, and this imbalance is not simply a reflection of a naturally skewed network.

Figure 4(b) shows that circle membership is measurable across consecutive years, with Jaccard stability generally higher in the inner circles than in the outer ones. This is consistent with the frequency imbalance: the innermost circles contain the ego’s most frequently and persistently contacted alters, whose high interaction rates make them less likely to migrate across layers from year to year. The outer circles, by contrast, aggregate a larger and more heterogeneous pool of contacts whose annual frequencies are more variable, resulting in lower membership stability. This pattern suggests that despite the structural

imbalance observed in circle sizes, the high-frequency core is not an artifact of year-to-year fluctuations but reflects a stable set of privileged relationships.

The frequency profile in Figure 4(c) reveals the cause of the structural imbalance in Figure 4(a). The innermost empirical circles reach annual frequencies close to 2,000 messages—far above both the Dunbar weekly-contact reference of 53 per year and the Enron inner-circle value of approximately 35. Even the outermost empirical layer exceeds 100 messages per year, which is itself above the Dunbar threshold for the most active layer. Jmail therefore contains a few extremely frequent contacts and a much larger group of alters that are less intense only in relative terms, but still highly active in absolute terms. This extreme skew causes MeanShift to fragment the high-frequency core into very sparse inner circles while placing many still-active contacts in the broad outer layer. The empirical layering is therefore hard to interpret in Dunbar terms, which motivates a more principled diagnostic approach.

Dunbar-reference circles and scaling To diagnose this distortion more precisely, we apply the canonical Dunbar frequency thresholds directly to Jmail as a baseline. Specifically, we ignore the circles created by MeanShift and assign alters to circles based on the canonical Dunbar frequency thresholds. E.g., with reference to Table 1, a frequency higher than once a week would put the alter in circle 1.

Figure 5 shows that the result is not simply a noisy version of an ordinary ego network: the unscaled assignment produces an almost reversed profile, with many alters falling into inner or intermediate Dunbar circles and the outermost yearly-contact layer weakly represented. This reversal does not indicate an absence of structure. Rather, it confirms that Jmail is a selected pool of high-interest alters whose baseline interaction frequencies are already high relative to the canonical Dunbar scale, so the standard thresholds are not appropriate as-is. The solution is not to abandon Dunbar’s model, but to adapt its frequency scale to Jmail’s communication regime while preserving its structural logic.

Fig. 4: Jmail — Empirical MeanShift circle structure of the main ego.

Fig. 5: Jmail — Dunbar-reference circle structure under canonical frequency thresholds.

We therefore rescale the Dunbar frequency ladder while preserving the canonical circle sizes and their ordering. The rescaling is anchored to one of Dunbar’s circles: for a given reference circle of size N , we rank the ego’s active alters by annual frequency in each year, take the frequency of the N th-ranked alter, and average these values across the observation period. This empirical frequency is then divided by the Dunbar contact threshold associated with that circle, yielding a scaling factor that re-expresses the full Dunbar ladder in Jmail’s frequency units without forcing any particular layered structure to appear. We use the support clique ($N = 5$, weekly contact) as the reference circle. We anchor the scaling procedure to the support clique because it is the most stable and cognitively constrained layer in Dunbar’s model. As the ego’s strongest and most regularly maintained relationships, these ties are less affected by contextual and platform-specific variability than broader outer layers. In Jmail, the support clique also provides the clearest empirical boundary in an otherwise highly skewed communication environment, making it a robust reference for adapting Dunbar’s frequency scale to the archive’s unusually high interaction intensity. The resulting scaling factor using the support clique is 17. A sensitivity check anchored to the sympathy group ($N = 15$, monthly contact) is reported in Appendix C and yields consistent results.

Figure 6 shows that, once the Dunbar ladder is anchored to the observed support-clique boundary, a clearer layered structure emerges. The rescaled circles recover a more interpretable Dunbar-like organization in size, preserve measurable temporal stability, and retain a decreasing frequency gradient from the high-contact core toward broader layers. Importantly, this structure is not an artifact of the scaling procedure: because scaling only changes the frequency unit of the reference thresholds, the emergence of coherent layers is not guaranteed by construction. This result shows that Jmail does contain Dunbar-like layered organization, but that it is obscured when standard methods are applied

Fig. 6: Jmail — Top-5 scaled Dunbar-reference circles.

without accounting for the archive’s unusually high communication intensity. A natural remaining question is whether these recovered layers reflect genuine social relationships or are simply an artifact of the main ego’s outgoing activity.

Key Finding 2: Jmail requires scaled Dunbar-reference thresholds

Jmail does not behave like a complete ego network with many weak peripheral contacts, but like a selected pool of high-interest alters. This extreme frequency regime distorts both data-driven clustering and unscaled Dunbar thresholds. Once Dunbar frequencies are scaled to the activity of the high-contact core, the main layered structure re-emerges, showing that Dunbar’s model remains useful as a scalable structural reference.

Reciprocity of scaled ego-network layers. The scaled layers reorganize Jmail’s alters into a more interpretable structure, but a residual concern remains: are these layers a genuine reflection of social relationships, or simply an artifact of the main ego’s outgoing activity? To address this, for each year we retain alters for whom communication is observed in both directions (main ego \rightarrow alter and alter \rightarrow main ego) and test whether alters placed in higher-frequency Dunbar circles also contact the main ego more frequently in their own outgoing communication. Table 4 reports the results for the last three years; full year-wise tables for all scaling variants are reported in Appendix D. The overall ego–alter frequency correlations are consistently and strongly positive, increasing from $r = 0.91$ in 2016 to $r = 0.95$ in 2018, confirming that the scaled layers capture genuine bidirectional relationships rather than one-sided ego activity. Circle-wise correlations are more variable, particularly in the innermost circle where few reciprocal alters are available. The middle and outer circles are more informative: Circle 3 contains 14, 14, and 10 reciprocal alters in 2016–2018 with positive correlations throughout, and Circle 4 remains positively correlated in the same period. Finally, the MeanShift composition column confirms that the scaled

Dunbar circles consolidate the over-fragmented empirical core into broader, more coherent layers, whereas the unscaled assignment collapses many heterogeneous data-driven rings into a single Dunbar circle.

Key Finding 3: Scaled Jmail layers are reciprocally meaningful

The scaled layers reflect genuine bidirectional relationships: alters in higher-frequency circles also contact the main ego more actively, with overall correlations consistently above $r = 0.91$. Frequency scaling thus recovers both structural interpretability and relational meaningfulness.

Table 4: Jmail — Reciprocity under top-5 scaled Dunbar-reference circles (last three years). The column “MS” refers to the MeanShift clustering, reporting the circle (C) and the relative alter count (#).

Year	Overall		Circle 1			Circle 2			Circle 3			Circle 4		
	n	r	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS
2016	37	0.91	3	-0.11	C1#1, C2#2	6	0.21	C5#4, C6#2	14	0.62	C6#14	7	0.55	C6#7
2017	34	0.92	3	0.34	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1	6	0.75	C6#3, C7#3	14	0.89	C7#14	4	0.94	C7#4
2018	33	0.95	2	-1.00	C1#1, C2#1	6	0.34	C5#2, C6#4	10	0.40	C7#10	5	0.86	C7#5

5 Conclusion

This paper examined whether layered ego-network structure can be recovered from email communication. Using Enron as a workplace benchmark, we showed that email-derived ego networks can reproduce part of the Dunbar-like organization observed in other communication media: small inner circles are visible, and the outermost observed layer is close to the Dunbar ~ 50 circle, while the broader ~ 150 circle is not recovered. We then analysed Jmail as a contrasting, high-frequency ego-centered archive. The case-specific nature of Jmail is therefore part of the empirical contribution: it provides a rare public setting in which layered ego-network methods can be tested on a highly ego-centered, socially salient email archive. The results show that Jmail should not be interpreted as an ordinary email ego network with higher activity, but as a selected pool of high-interest alters where weak and occasional contacts are comparatively underrepresented. This affects both data-driven and reference-based approaches: MeanShift separates a few extremely frequent alters into narrow inner circles, while unscaled Dunbar thresholds produce an almost reversed ego-network profile. When the Dunbar frequency scale is adapted to the high-contact core, a clearer layered structure emerges. Finally, reciprocity analysis suggests that the reconstructed layers are not only artifacts of the main ego’s activity. Reciprocal active alters show positive ego–alter frequency correlations, and the scaled circles provide a smoother interpretation of the empirical MeanShift structure. Overall, the findings suggest that Dunbar’s model remains useful for email ego networks. Enron shows that Dunbar-like layering can emerge in ordinary workplace email, while Jmail shows that selective high-frequency archives require normalization before the same structure becomes interpretable. Future work should extend this analysis to additional email archives and examine whether similar scaling behavior appears in other high-intensity communication environments.

References

1. Arnaboldi, V., Conti, M., Passarella, A., Pezzoni, F.: Analysis of ego network structure in online social networks. In: 2012 International Conference on Privacy, Security, Risk and Trust and 2012 International Conference on Social Computing. pp. 31–40. IEEE (2012)
2. Arnaboldi, V., Passarella, A., Conti, M., Dunbar, R.I.: Online social networks: human cognitive constraints in Facebook and Twitter personal graphs. Elsevier (2015)
3. Barabasi, A.L.: The origin of bursts and heavy tails in human dynamics. *Nature* **435**(7039), 207–211 (2005)
4. Di Cursi, F., Boldrini, C., Passarella, A., Conti, M.: A herd of young mastodonts: the user-centered footprints of newcomers after twitter acquisition. In: 2024 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData). pp. 6992–7001. IEEE (2024)
5. Diesner, J., Carley, K.M.: Exploration of communications networks from the enron email corpus. In: Proc. of the Workshop on Link Analysis, Counterterrorism and Security, SIAM Intl. Conf. on Data Mining. pp. 3–14 (2005)
6. Dunbar, R.I.: The social brain hypothesis. *Evolutionary Anthropology: Issues, News, and Reviews: Issues, News, and Reviews* **6**(5), 178–190 (1998)
7. Dunbar, R.I., Arnaboldi, V., Conti, M., Passarella, A.: The structure of online social networks mirrors those in the offline world. *Social networks* **43**, 39–47 (2015)
8. Eckmann, J.P., Moses, E., Sergi, D.: Entropy of dialogues creates coherent structures in e-mail traffic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **101**(40), 14333–14337 (2004)
9. Golder, S.A., Wilkinson, D.M., Huberman, B.A.: Rhythms of social interaction: Messaging within a massive online network. In: *Communities and Technologies 2007: Proceedings of the Third Communities and Technologies Conference*, Michigan State University 2007. pp. 41–66. Springer (2007)
10. Klimt, B., Yang, Y.: The enron corpus: A new dataset for email classification research. In: *European conference on machine learning*. pp. 217–226. Springer (2004)
11. Kossinets, G., Watts, D.J.: Empirical analysis of an evolving social network. *science* **311**(5757), 88–90 (2006)
12. Leskovec, J., Krevl, A.: SNAP Datasets: Stanford large network dataset collection. <http://snap.stanford.edu/data> (Jun 2014)
13. Mac Carron, P., Kaski, K., Dunbar, R.: Calling dunbar’s numbers. *Social Networks* **47**, 151–155 (2016)
14. McCallum, A., Wang, X., Corrada-Emmanuel, A.: Topic and role discovery in social networks with experiments on enron and academic email. *Journal of artificial intelligence research* **30**, 249–272 (2007)
15. Oard, D.W., Webber, W., Kirsch, D., Golitsynskiy, S.: Avocado research email collection. Web Download (2015), IDC2015T03
16. Tyler, J.R., Wilkinson, D.M., Huberman, B.A.: E-mail as spectroscopy: Automated discovery of community structure within organizations. *The Information Society* **21**(2), 143–153 (2005)

Appendix

A Preprocessing for Jmail identity consolidation

Table 2 reports the datasets at two levels of representation: the raw expanded interaction table and the selected ego-network view used in the analysis. For Jmail, the raw representation is obtained by expanding each email into directed sender–recipient interaction rows. Thus, a message addressed to multiple recipients contributes multiple interaction records, while preserving the original message metadata. This representation is useful for describing the scale of the archive, but it is not yet suitable for ego-network analysis because identities are still represented as raw textual strings and may contain redaction, parsing, and formatting artifacts.

The selected Jmail view reported in Table 2 is obtained after applying the preprocessing and identity consolidation procedure described in this appendix. The main actor is identified through the dedicated column available in the structured data. The consolidation step is therefore essential primarily for the actor’s alters: because the source documents are redacted and partially processed, the same individual may appear under multiple textual variants, aliases, truncated names, or formatting-contaminated forms. The purpose of the procedure is to assign these alter mentions to stable, auditable person-level identifiers, so that the ego-centered network of the main actor can be reconstructed consistently. The resulting selected Jmail ego network contains one ego and 4,299 alters.

The procedure should be understood as a conservative rule-based identity-resolution step, rather than as an attempt to reconstruct ground-truth identities without error. Its design prioritizes the avoidance of false merges over the recovery of every possible variant of the same individual. Consequently, some unresolved variants may remain split across distinct identifiers, but this reduces the risk of artificially merging different alters and inflating ego–alter interaction counts.

In summary, the preprocessing pipeline consists of five steps: (i) expanding emails into directed sender–recipient interactions; (ii) removing promotional, invalid, missing, placeholder, and malformed identity strings; (iii) normalizing candidate alter identity strings; (iv) constructing a conservative name-similarity graph over valid identity variants; and (v) extracting connected components as consolidated person-level identifiers.

Interaction expansion and initial cleaning. The procedure starts from the expanded sender–recipient interactions. Each email is converted into one or more directed interaction rows, depending on the number of recipients, while retaining the associated message metadata. Promotional emails are then removed by exploiting the corresponding field available in the dataset. Rows containing missing or placeholder senders or recipients are also dropped, including empty values and textual placeholders such as `nan` and `none`. In addition, sender or recipient strings shorter than two characters are excluded.

The remaining identity strings are sanitized by removing characters that are clearly attributable to the parsing of redacted documents or to formatting noise. This step removes the most evident non-name artifacts while preserving the raw textual identity layer needed for the subsequent consolidation of alter names.

Identity normalization and candidate filtering. After the initial cleaning stage, alter identities are still represented as free-form strings and therefore cannot yet be treated as stable person-level identifiers. We address this issue through a dedicated consolidation procedure applied to the union of sender and recipient names that appear in the interaction table. The objective is to map multiple surface variants of the same alter to a single canonical identifier, while keeping the merging criteria sufficiently strict to reduce the risk of erroneous confluents.

The first step consists of an additional normalization of the name strings. All names are lowercased and stripped of surrounding whitespace. Character repetitions of length three or more are reduced to two consecutive identical characters, multiple consecutive dots are collapsed to a single dot, and whitespace is normalized. This produces the cleaned representation used for identity clustering.

A validity filter is then applied before any pairwise comparison is performed. Validity is assessed after removing email substrings from the cleaned name. Only strings whose email-stripped form has length between 4 and 70 characters are retained. In addition, a name is considered clusterable only if it contains at least two whitespace-separated components. The only single-token exception is `gmail`, which is explicitly whitelisted as a known alias. The correspondence between cleaned strings and their original variants is retained, so that the final cluster assignments can be propagated back to the interaction table.

Similarity measures and name anchors. Pairwise similarity is computed over the set of unique valid cleaned names. The main similarity score is the *token-sort ratio*, a fuzzy string-matching measure in which the components of two names are first reordered alphabetically and then compared. This makes the score robust to permutations, such as inversions between given name and surname, while still penalizing insertions, deletions, and substitutions.

In parallel, each name is decomposed into a first-name token and a surname proxy. The surname proxy is obtained by scanning the tokens from right to left and selecting the last token whose length is at least four characters; if no such token exists, the final token is used. This provides a more stable surname anchor than relying on the raw final component alone, especially when names include middle tokens, email contamination, or residual formatting artifacts.

Two names are considered to have compatible first-name tokens if their first tokens are identical, or if one is a prefix of the other and the longer token has length at least four. This allows a full given name and a mildly truncated variant to remain comparable, while preventing very short fragments from triggering accidental matches.

Similarity graph construction. Identity consolidation is performed by constructing a graph whose nodes are valid cleaned names. An edge is added between two

Table 5: Identity-linking rules used to construct the Jmail name-similarity graph.

Rule	Linking condition
Explicit bridges	Hand-crafted links for recurrent redaction, parsing, or email-related artifacts identified through inspection of the clustered names.
Strict typo rule	Compatible first-name tokens and surname Levenshtein distance equal to one, with maximum surname-length difference equal to one.
Base-form rule	Surname similarity ≥ 95 and base-form similarity ≥ 95 , where the base form consists of the first token and the surname proxy.
Core merge rule	Compatible first-name tokens, surname similarity ≥ 92 , and token-sort similarity ≥ 93 .

names whenever at least one conservative linking rule is satisfied. The rules are summarized in Table 5.

The explicit bridges address a small number of recurrent artifacts that would be difficult to capture through generic string similarity alone. These cases involve OCR-like distortions, redaction artifacts, or email-related fragments that were found, through iterative inspection, to generate disproportionately large and error-prone components. Because they involve recurrent and structurally important actors in the collection, they are treated as explicit special cases rather than being left to the generic similarity rules alone. These bridges are limited to recurrent, manually verified artifacts and are not used as a general mechanism for relaxing the similarity thresholds. Analogous distortions observed only in very small components were not handled separately, since their impact on the global clustering structure was limited.

The strict typo rule captures highly local surname distortions. Two names are connected when their first-name tokens are compatible and their surname proxies differ by exactly one edit. Edit distance is measured with the Levenshtein distance, i.e., the minimum number of single-character insertions, deletions, or substitutions required to transform one string into the other. The additional constraint on surname-length difference prevents broader or less reliable matches from being accepted under this rule.

The base-form rule is designed for cases in which middle names, additional tokens, or email contamination reduce the similarity of the full string even though the core identity remains clear. The base form retains only the first token and the surname proxy. A link is added only when both the surname similarity and the base-form similarity are at least 95 on a 0–100 fuzzy-matching scale. This rule is therefore intentionally conservative: the two names must be almost identical both in their surname anchor and in their reduced two-token representation.

The core merge rule handles the remaining high-confidence matches. Two names are linked when they have compatible first-name tokens, surname similarity of at least 92, and overall token-sort similarity of at least 93. The thresholds

were chosen conservatively after manual inspection of candidate matches, prioritizing the avoidance of false merges over the recovery of every possible textual variant. The use of separate surname-level and full-name thresholds reduces the risk of merging names that look globally similar for superficial reasons but diverge in surname structure, or names that share a similar surname while differing substantially in the full expression.

Cluster extraction and canonicalization. Once all admissible pairwise links have been added, identity clusters are obtained as connected components of the similarity graph. This means that names need not match directly to be assigned to the same cluster: they may also be connected through a chain of highly plausible intermediate variants. This transitive closure is useful because identity variation in the collection is often gradual rather than concentrated in a single corrupted form. At the same time, transitivity operates only over edges produced by the strict local rules described above, rather than over unconstrained similarity.

For each connected component, the longest name string is used as the canonical textual representative of the cluster. Every original raw name that contributed to one of the cleaned forms in that component is then mapped to the same person-level identifier in the interaction table. The main actor is handled separately through the dedicated dataset column that identifies him in the structured records. This column is used to anchor the ego of the analysis, while the identity-consolidation procedure is used to assign stable identifiers to the alters connected to him.

The resulting mapping is applied back to the interaction table, so that both sender-side and recipient-side occurrences receive stable person-level identifiers whenever they correspond to consolidated alter identities. In parallel, for each identifier we retain the full set of associated textual variants, preserving traceability to the original observed strings. The final output is a consolidated interaction table in which corrupted, partial, or format-specific renderings of the same individual are represented as a single node. The selected Jmail ego network reported in Table 2 is then derived from this consolidated representation by retaining the ego-centered communication view of the main actor used in the analysis.

B Frequency Distribution Diagnostics

(a) Main ego → active alters

(b) Active alters → main ego

Fig. 7: Jmail — Annual frequency distributions in both ego–alter directions under canonical Dunbar-reference circles.

C Scaled Dunbar Reference Sensitivity

Table 6: Jmail — Scaling factors for Dunbar-reference thresholds.

Top-N	Scale reference value	Scaling ratio
5	886.54	17
15	436.88	36.41

(a) Circle sizes across years

(b) Stability of circle membership across consecutive years

(c) Average annual frequency by circle

Fig. 8: Jmail — Top-15 scaled Dunbar-reference circles.

D Reciprocity Sensitivity Tables

Table 7: Jmail — Reciprocity under unscaled Dunbar-reference circles. The column “MS” refers to the Meanshift clustering, reporting the circle (C) and the relative alter count (#).

Year	Overall		Circle 1			Circle 2			Circle 3			Circle 4		
	n	r	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS
2009	21	0.57	13	0.34	C4#4, C5#7, C6#2	2	1.00	C6#2	-	-	-	-	-	-
2010	33	0.78	22	0.77	C2#2, C4#3, C5#7, C6#10	3	-0.29	C6#3	-	-	-	-	-	-
2011	31	0.72	26	0.71	C1#1, C2#1, C5#1, C6#6, C7#17	2	-1.00	C7#2	1	-	C7#1	-	-	-
2012	32	0.74	24	0.72	C1#1, C2#1, C5#1, C6#2, C7#9, C8#10	4	-0.87	C8#4	-	-	-	-	-	-
2013	37	0.83	23	0.81	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1, C4#1, C5#2, C6#3, C7#14	4	0.10	C7#4	-	-	-	-	-	-
2014	38	0.89	22	0.89	C1#1, C2#2, C4#1, C5#2, C6#5, C7#11	3	1.00	C7#3	2	1.00	C7#2	-	-	-
2015	37	0.81	25	0.80	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1, C4#2, C5#20	4	-0.34	C5#4	2	1.00	C5#2	-	-	-
2016	37	0.91	22	0.90	C1#1, C2#2, C5#5, C6#14	5	0.49	C6#5	3	0.84	C6#3	-	-	-
2017	34	0.92	19	0.90	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1, C4#1, C6#4, C7#11	8	0.76	C7#8	1	-	C7#1	-	-	-
2018	33	0.95	19	0.95	C1#1, C2#1, C5#2, C6#6, C7#9	7	0.33	C7#7	1	-	C7#1	-	-	-

Table 8: Jmail — Reciprocity under top-5 scaled Dunbar-reference circles. The column “MS” refers to the Meanshift clustering, reporting the circle (C) and the relative alter count (#).

Year	Overall		Circle 1			Circle 2			Circle 3			Circle 4		
	n	r	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS
2009	21	0.57	-	-	-	3	-0.90	C4#2, C5#1	11	0.56	C5#6, C6#5	2	1.00	C6#2
2010	33	0.78	1	-	C2#1	8	0.39	C4#3, C5#5	12	0.55	C6#12	4	-0.20	C6#4
2011	31	0.72	2	-1.00	C1#1, C2#1	12	0.78	C5#1, C6#5, C7#6	13	0.04	C7#13	1	-	C7#1
2012	32	0.74	2	-1.00	C1#1, C2#1	10	0.37	C6#2, C7#8	9	0.25	C8#9	2	-1.00	C8#2
2013	37	0.83	4	0.75	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1, C4#1	7	0.77	C5#1, C6#3, C7#3	11	0.24	C7#11	4	0.63	C7#4
2014	38	0.89	3	0.99	C1#1, C2#2	6	0.86	C4#1, C5#2, C6#3	12	0.57	C7#12	8	0.41	C7#8
2015	37	0.81	3	-0.72	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1	6	0.87	C4#2, C5#4	14	0.52	C5#14	4	0.63	C5#4
2016	37	0.91	3	-0.11	C1#1, C2#2	6	0.21	C5#4, C6#2	14	0.62	C6#14	7	0.55	C6#7
2017	34	0.92	3	0.34	C1#1, C2#1, C3#1	6	0.75	C6#3, C7#3	14	0.89	C7#14	4	0.94	C7#4
2018	33	0.95	2	-1.00	C1#1, C2#1	6	0.34	C5#2, C6#4	10	0.40	C7#10	5	0.86	C7#5

Table 9: Jmail — Reciprocity under top-15 scaled Dunbar-reference circles. The column “MS” refers to the Meanshift clustering, reporting the circle (C) and the relative alter count (#).

Year	Overall		Circle 1			Circle 2			Circle 3			Circle 4		
	n	r	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS	n	r	MS
2009	21	0.57	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	0.82	C4#3, C5#5, C6#1	6	0.63	C6#6
2010	33	0.78	-	-	-	4	0.86	C2#1, C4#2, C5#1	8	0.05	C5#2, C6#6	10	0.47	C6#10
2011	31	0.72	1	-	C1#1	3	0.03	C5#1, C6#2	16	0.82	C6#2, C7#14	4	0.86	C7#4
2012	32	0.74	1	-	C1#1	2	1.00	C5#1, C6#1	11	0.67	C7#6, C8#5	5	0.57	C8#5
2013	37	0.83	1	-	C1#1	5	0.89	C3#1, C4#1, C5#2, C6#1	14	0.59	C6#1, C7#13	8	-0.12	C7#8
2014	38	0.89	1	-	C1#1	3	0.97	C2#2, C4#1	16	0.44	C5#1, C6#5, C7#10	11	0.13	C7#11
2015	37	0.81	1	-	C1#1	3	1.00	C2#1, C4#2	15	0.77	C5#15	10	0.26	C5#10
2016	37	0.91	1	-	C1#1	1	-	C2#1	16	0.64	C5#3, C6#13	10	0.75	C6#10
2017	34	0.92	2	-1.00	C1#1, C2#1	3	0.90	C3#1, C4#1, C6#1	13	0.54	C6#2, C7#11	12	0.66	C7#12
2018	33	0.95	1	-	C1#1	1	-	C5#1	10	0.65	C6#3, C7#7	11	0.50	C7#11